

NONDESTRUCTIVE TEST OF CRITICAL LOADS OF COMPOSITE PLATES AND SHELLS

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ABSTRACT

The structural reliability of composite plates and shells is a very important problem in the application of composite materials. For vehicle structures the load bearing capacity of which is controlled by the buckling of plates and shells, nondestructive test of critical loads is provided to guarantee the structural reliability. First, the static method and dynamic method of critical load nondestructive test are briefly reviewed in this paper, then C/E composite triangular grid shells have been tested nondestructively by dynamical methods to obtain the critical pressures. Two sets of test results are provided in this paper. Low-load level modal test method is proved to be effective. It will be widely used in nondestructive test of critical loads. At the end of this paper, zero-load modal test method is discussed and may be used as the supplement of low-load level modal test method at least.

KEYWORDS: Composites; Plates; Shells; Critical load; Nondestructive test.

1. INTRODUCTION

In aerospace engineering, composite materials have been used in main loaded structures for their high specific strength and specific stiffness. The performance of composite structure is dependent on the fiber, the resin and the fabrication process, and their performance scatter may be large, so it is not easy to guarantee their reliability by ordinary methods. The structural reliability of composite structures has become a very important problem in the application of composite materials.

In order to guarantee the reliability of composite structures, a quality test and control sys-

tem is necessary. It contains raw material examination, fabrication process examination, detection of defects of finished products, nondestructive test of bearing capacity of products and sampling destructive test of bearing capacity of products, as shown in figure 1.

Nondestructive test of bearing capacity of products is one of the most important tools for the structural reliability evaluation of composite products.

For vehicle structure the bearing capacity of which is controlled by the buckling of plates and shells, nondestructive test of critical loads has important value in aerospace engineering.

Figure 1 A quality test and control system of composite materials

2. BRIEF DESCRIPTION OF NONDESTRUCTIVE TEST OF CRITICAL LOADS OF PLATES AND SHELLS

The nondestructive test methods of critical loads may be classified as statical methods and dynamic methods

2.1 Statical Method It is called the statical method that the critical load of structure is predicted by using the relation between the deformation or strain and the load. The Southwell plot method is a well-known statical method. It is derived from the small deflection linear theory. Its fundamental formula is as follows

$$\frac{\delta}{P} = \frac{\delta + \delta_0}{P_{cr}} \quad (1)$$

where P – compressive load;
 δ – deflection under load P ;
 δ_0 – initial deflection;
 P_{cr} – critical load.

Taking δ / P as ordinate and δ as abscissa, the equation (1) may be shown as a straight line in figure 2, the critical load equals the reciprocal of its slope.

The Southwell plot method is applicable for predicting the critical loads of plates [1,2,3].

Figure 2 Southwell plot method

2.2 Dynamic Method It is called the dynamic method that the critical load of structure is predicted by using the vibration parameters of structure. The theoretical basis of the dynamic method is that the stability problem of structure is similar to the vibration problem. Both are eigenvalue problems under certain boundary conditions.

Low-load level modal test method is one of dynamic methods. It is based on the concept that the natural frequency in the buckle mode shape goes to zero when the critical buckling load is reached, and there is the linear interaction between the square of the frequency and the applied load as shown in figure 3.

Its basic formula is as follows

$$f^2 = f_0^2 \left(1 - \frac{P}{P_{cr}}\right) \quad (2)$$

where f_0 – the natural frequency in the buckle mode shape under zero-load;

P – applied load;

P_{cr} – critical buckling load;

f – the natural frequency in the buckle mode shape under P .

Figure 3 Linear interaction between the square of natural frequency and applied load

The natural frequency of structure is the measurement of global stiffness, unlike strain and deflection which are local. As a result, the low-load level modal test method has several ad-

vantages over the Southwell plot method which is based upon single-point information. The difficulty in the low-load level modal test method is that when $P \rightarrow P_{cr}$ the nonlinear interaction between f^2 and P appears. It brings the uncertainty to the prediction of the critical load. It is the source of the difficulty that the equation (2) is derived from the small deflection linear theory. In order to solve this question, Schneider et al. [4,5] suggest to take $f_0^2 / 4$ as the cut off frequency for predicting P_{cr} , as shown in figure 4.

Figure 4 The cut off frequency for predicting P_{CR}

The low-load level modal test method is applicable for predicting the critical loads of shells [4,5].

3. NONDESTRUCTIVE TEST OF CRITICAL LOADS OF COMPOSITE RIB-STIFFENED SHELLS

3.1 Basic Equations First, composite rib-stiffened shells are translated to a kind of special orthotropic laminated shells and then stiffness parameters $[A]$, $[B]$, $[C]$ are calculated [6]. Introducing inertial term $-\rho\delta\frac{\partial^2 W}{\partial t^2}$ (where ρ is the density of composite materials, δ is the equivalent thickness of shell, t is time) into the stability equations which are based on the small deflection linear theory, we get the dynamic equilibrium equations of shells. The deflection functions selected should reflect vibration feature, as follows

$$\left. \begin{aligned} U &= \bar{U} \cos(ax) \cos(by) \exp(j \omega_{mn} t) \\ V &= \bar{V} \sin(ax) \sin(by) \exp(j \omega_{mn} t) \\ W &= \bar{W} \sin(ax) \cos(by) \exp(j \omega_{mn} t) \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (3)$$

where $a = m\pi / L$;

$b = n / R$;

ω_{mn} - the natural circular frequency of the mode (m, n) ;

m - meridional half waves;

n - circumferential full waves.

Substituting the equation(3) into the dynamic equilibrium equations of shells we get

$$\left. \begin{aligned} -K_{11}\bar{U} + K_{12}\bar{V} + K_{13}\bar{W} &= 0 \\ K_{12}\bar{U} - K_{22}\bar{V} + K_{23}\bar{W} &= 0 \\ K_{13}\bar{U} + K_{23}\bar{V} - (K_{33} + N_x^0 a^2 + N_y^0 b^2 - \delta\rho\omega_{mn}^2)\bar{W} &= 0 \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (4)$$

where $K_{11} \dots K_{33}$ and N_x^0, N_y^0 are the same as the equation (8),(5) in reference [6].

From equation (4) we get

$$N_x^0 a^2 + N_y^0 b^2 - \delta\rho\omega_{mn}^2 = -K_{33} + \frac{2K_{12}K_{13}K_{23} + K_{11}K_{23}^2 + K_{22}K_{13}^2}{K_{11}K_{22} - K_{12}^2} \quad (5)$$

If the applied load is only the external pressure, we have $N_x^0 = 0, N_y^0 = -PR$. Substituting these expressions into equation (5) we get

$$P + \frac{4\pi^2 \rho \delta f_{mn}^2}{Rb^2} = \frac{1}{Rb^2} \cdot \left(K_{33} - \frac{2K_{12}K_{13}K_{23} + K_{11}K_{23}^2 + K_{22}K_{13}^2}{K_{11}K_{22} - K_{12}^2} \right) \quad (6)$$

where f_{mn} - the natural frequency of the mode (m,n), Hz.

From the equation (6), f_{mn} goes down linearly with increasing P for any mode (m,n). Hence, for the buckling mode (m_1, n_1) there is the following equation

$$P + \frac{4\pi^2 \rho \delta f_{m_1, n_1}^2}{Rb^2} = P_{cr} \quad (7)$$

where

$$P_{cr} = \left\{ \frac{1}{Rb^2} \cdot \left(K_{33} - \frac{2K_{12}K_{13}K_{23} + K_{11}K_{23}^2 + K_{22}K_{13}^2}{K_{11}K_{22} - K_{12}^2} \right) \right\}_{m=m_1, n=n_1}$$

From equation (7) we know that the natural frequency feature of buckling mode (m_1, n_1) can be used to predict the critical pressure of shells, P_{cr} .

3.2 Low-load Level Modal Test

3.2.1 Test specimens C/E composite triangular grid cylindrical shells are selected as the test specimens whose dimensions are listed in table 1.

Table 1

Number of test specimens	Length L	Radius R	Laminated angle of skin	Rib parameters			
				Angle θ	Width B	Height H	Space s
1	300	115	$90^\circ/50^\circ/-50^\circ/50^\circ/90^\circ$	30°	1.9	3.8	52.13
				-30°	1.9	3.8	52.13
				90°	1.9	3.8	52.13
2	300	115	$50^\circ/-50^\circ/50^\circ/-50^\circ/50^\circ$	30°	1.9	3.8	52.13
				-30°	1.9	3.8	52.13
				90°	1.9	3.8	52.13

Note: 1. the unit of dimension is mm:

2. the thickness of 90° lamina is 0.25 mm, the thickness of other laminae is 0.2 mm ;

3. the density of C/E composite materials is $\rho = 1.5 \times 10^{-3} \text{ kg/cm}^3$.

3.2.2 Test As the above description, the main work of the low-load level modal test used to predict the critical load of shells is to measure the low-order modal parameters of shells at low-load levels. The sketch of test scheme is shown in figure 5. The force hammer excitation method was adopted in this paper.

Figure 5 The sketch of test scheme

The knocking points (A) are located equally along circumferential lines and generating lines on inner surface of test specimen (64 points in all). An accelerometer is fixed at point B which is any point selected on inner surface of test specimen.

The force excitation input and the acceleration response of the test specimen are amplified by the charge amplifiers respectively, and then sent into FFT analyzer. The transfer functions are obtained from FFT analyzer, and sent into the computer. The low-order modal parameters are identified by the aid of computer and special software, and are printed by the printer.

The key point of critical pressure nondestructive test is how to perform the loaded modal test. If the external pressure is loaded by vacuum-pumping on the inside of test specimen as used to be done, the highest pressure value is less than $9.80665 \times 10^5 Pa$ (1 atm), but for some vehicles, for example re-entry vehicles, the highest external pressure in the loaded modal test are requested to be larger than $9.80665 \times 10^5 Pa$ (1 atm). Hence, the vacuum-pumping is not applicable to the re-entry vehicles. In this paper, the external pressure was loaded by pressing air into the space between the inside of the test equipment and the outside of test specimen. In this way, the influence of the loading medium to measuring the modal parameters of test specimen can be reduced. Because the load level usually does not exceed 60% of the bearing capacity of the test specimen, the loaded modal test by "pressing air" is safe and reliable. It has been proved that the loaded modal test by "pressing air" is satisfactory.

In order to examine the prediction of nondestructive test, the external pressure destructive tests by "pressing oil" were conducted after performing the loaded modal tests.

3.2.3

Test results and analyses Two sets of test results are shown in figure 6. It has been proved that the natural frequency squared of the buckling mode drops linearly with the external pressure increase. If the cut-off frequency squared is taken as $f_0^2 / 4$ (f_0 is the zero-load frequency of the buckling mode), the prediction values of critical pressures by the loaded modal tests agree with the failure pressures by the destructive tests. The differences between them are within 5% (see table 2).

It has been shown that if the highest level of load P reaches to 40~50% of the critical load P_{cr} , the prediction precision is up to the engineering requirements. Hence, the loaded modal test is nondestructive.

△ Failure pressure value tested

Figure 6 The loaded modal test results

Table 2

Number of test specimens	Prediction value of critical pressure, $10^5 Pa$	Failure pressure values tested $10^5 Pa$
1	11.96	11.52
2	10.30	10.79

Although the above theory and test studies on the loaded modal test are directed against the simple cylindrical shells, its basic principle is applicable to any complicated shells.

3.3 Zero-load Modal Test Method Let (m_1, n_1) is the buckling mode, values m_1, n_1 are given from the theoretical calculation. Let $f_{m_1, n_1, 0}$ is the zero-load frequency of the buckling mode (m_1, n_1) , there is the following relation from the formula (7)

$$P_{cr} = \left(\frac{4\pi^2 \rho \delta}{Rb^2} \right)_{n=n_1} f_{m_1, n_1, 0}^2 \tag{8}$$

The equation (8) is the theoretical basis of zero-load modal test method.

For the above two test specimens, the triangular grid cylindrical shells made of C/E composite materials, the predictions of zero-load modal test method are listed in table 3. Table 3 also gives their failure pressure values tested respectively, in order to compare them.

Table 3

Number of test specimens	f^2 measured $10^3 Hz^2$	Prediction value of the critical pressure from the equation (8), $10^5 Pa$	Failure pressure values tested $10^5 Pa$
1	1920	12.38	11.52
2	1700	10.96	10.79

It has been shown from the table 3 that the zero-load modal test method is effective to the simple cylindrical shells.

For the complicated shells, the critical pressure P_{cr} and the zero-load frequency of the buckling mode $f_{m_1, n_1, 0}$ are calculated by the structural analysis program based on the finite element method, and then we get coefficient

$$A = P_{cr} / f_{m_1, n_1, 0}^2 \quad (9)$$

The basic equation of the zero-load modal test method is the following

$$P_{cr} = KA f_{m_1, n_1, 0}^2 \quad (10)$$

where P_{cr} – the critical pressure predicted;
 K – the correcting coefficient obtained by a few of tests;
 A – the coefficient calculated from the formula (9);
 $f_{m_1, n_1, 0}$ – the buckling mode frequency measured by the zero-load modal test.

Both the critical pressure and the buckling mode frequency of the structure are determined by the general stiffness of this structure, so we can measure the buckling mode frequency of the structure to predict its critical pressure.

The advantage of zero-load modal test method is that the test works are simplified greatly. It is easy to be used in the engineering. It may be used as the supplement of low-load level modal test method at least.

4. SUMMARY

The structural reliability of composite structures is a very important problem in the application of composite materials. For vehicle structures the bearing capacities of which are controlled by the buckling of plates and shells, nondestructive test of critical loads has important engineering value and is one of the most important tools for the structural reliability evaluation.

The Southwell plot method is a well-known statical method and is applicable for predicting

the critical load of plates.

Low-load level modal test method is one of dynamic methods. The natural frequency is the measurement of global stiffness, unlike strain and deflection which are local and single-point information.

The advantage of zero-load modal test method is that test works are simplified greatly. It is easy to be used in the engineering. It may be used as the supplement of low-load level modal test method at least.

The use of the modal test method is recommended for all structural tests where failure due to general instability is concern.

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